

CAUSES OF HIGH FEVER IN CHILDREN WITHOUT APPROPRIATE
SYMPTOMS.

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Annotation: *This article the causes of high fever may be due to a virus or bacterial infection entering the body.*

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Every parent knows why the temperature rises, so it is necessary to call the hospital in the first case. The sooner the cause of the disease, the more effective the treatment process. Consider what can cause a high fever in a child without unpredictable symptoms. The causes of high fever may be due to a virus or bacterial infection entering the body. Without other symptoms in this condition, a high temperature can be observed for 1 day, after which additional symptoms appear. Sometimes these symptoms, especially with bacterial diseases, are recognized only by a specialist. Baby temperature can be a factor in overheating the body, which occurs very often, not only in summer but also in winter, when parents try to keep the baby warm. Reaction to the vaccine. Temperature in infants increases due to the body's response to the vaccine. The temperature does not exceed 38 degrees, but not in cases where children are hypersensitive to the drug used. Important to know! Any cause for a rise in temperature in a child should have appropriate symptoms that may appear immediately or after some time. Only doctors can recognize some of the symptoms, so don't expect the time when complications start in the child. To determine the relevant disease as accurately as possible, consider the above causes of high fever in an asymptomatic child. Overheating of the body. If a child has an asymptomatic fever, it is important to rule out unsafe overheating of the body. Excessive heat can occur not only in summer but also in winter. It can be a simple way to wrap a baby in a room where the air temperature in the room is not lower than 20 degrees. When the body overheats, the baby shows signs of anxiety, the baby becomes restless, sluggish and passive. When overheated, the temperature in a child over the age of one usually rises to 38-39 degrees. As a result of overheating of interest, an inflammatory process begins. If the child does not have a prolonged fever, parents can take the following precautions:

1. You can lower the temperature by airing the room. The temperature in the room where the baby is should be kept at 18-22 degrees. If the fever does not subside after a few hours, you should seek medical attention.

2. Overheating of the body can lead to a heat crisis, which can lead to many other complications. If there is an abnormality in the sun, take it into the lake and put a damp cloth on your forehead. Sure, a few parents take a thermometer with them while walking in the park, but it won't be hard to find a strong fever. First, the forehead becomes hot and the baby is passive and lethargic.

3. In newborns, high temperature clothing can be removed.

4. Give your baby water or juice to drink. And in the heat, be sure to encourage the child to drink regularly to prevent dehydration.

When very hot, antipyretic drugs should not be given, but only if the thermometer does not show a value above 39 degrees. In this case, consult a specialist immediately.

Viral infection. The virus enters the body in any way. Once the virus enters the body, the baby's temperature rises above 38 degrees. At first, no additional symptoms may appear, which is a misunderstanding of parents. In just two or three days there may be similar symptoms such as runny nose, cough, redness of the throat. On the first day, the virus affects the respiratory tract, so the baby may have a runny nose. It is not difficult for an experienced professional to detect a viral infection. Most parents can also think independently about whether a child has a cold. It is strictly forbidden to treat a cold yourself without a prescription. High temperatures are caused by infections in the mouth. These diseases include: Pharyngitis in acute form. Only a doctor can diagnose the presence of pharyngitis. Characteristic symptoms of pharyngitis: the presence of ulcers in the throat, rash and redness.

1. Herpes occurs in the form of fever, as well as blisters in the form of sores, rashes and redness on the tonsils and back of the throat.

2. Angina Most often, it affects children as young as 7 months.

Angina is classified as a bacterial disease, so it can be treated with antibiotics. Antibiotics are not required for sore throat and the doctor treating pharyngitis should make a decision. In children 10 months to 2 years of age, asymptomatic fever may be a sign of a disease such as a sudden rash. The reasons for the rise in temperature are various viruses. The main symptoms of the disease:

- Strong heat up to 40 degrees;
- rash;
- swollen lymph nodes.

All symptoms of the disease disappear after 5 days. Typically, these symptoms last for 4 days and do not require treatment other than reducing the temperature to an optimal value below 38 degrees. According to statistics, 70% of children under the age of two are associated with exanthema. Urinary tract infection. Often in infants, the temperature rises, which may be a sign of the development of urinary tract complications. This is especially true in children. Antipyretic drugs are used to reduce fever: Panadol, Paracetamol, Ibuprofen. If the hyperthermia remains low on the first day and rises to febrile values on the second and third days, you should immediately ask the child to help with antipyretics. If the temperature drops, consult a specialist for assistance.

REFERENCES:

1.Q.Inomov, M.G'aniyeva. *Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi.* –T.: G'G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2007. 2.Проект усовершенствования медсестринского образования в Узбекистане. учебная программа и руководства по преподаванию. Представительство JICA в Узбекистане. Т.,2008. 3.A.J.Hamrayev, M.A.Xamedova. *Xirurgiya.* –T.: «O'qituvchi», 2002. 4.Ya.Allayorov, Ya.Tojiboyev. *Favqulotda vaziyatlarda tez tibbiy yordam asoslari.* –T.: «Zar qalam», 2005.

